

Deliverable D.1.1.1

Inventory of existing datasets in Belgian heritage science research groups

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ABSTRACT

Heritage science is a multidisciplinary field that connects the natural sciences and the humanities to study cultural heritage objects. Although the sector in Belgium possesses advanced analytical capabilities, research data is currently scattered across different institutions and often stored in local silos. This fragmentation makes scientific data difficult to find and reuse according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. The DIGILAB.be project aims to address these challenges by establishing a federated network of repositories. Under this model, partner institutions maintain control over their own data while the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA) provides a central search interface through its BALaT platform.

This deliverable, D.1.1.1, provides a high-level inventory of the data management habits and commitments of the project's main research groups, including the Royal Museums of Art and History (KMKG-MRAH) and the Universities of Antwerp, Liège, and Ghent. Consultations reveal that while these groups have strong publication records, they typically lack established practices for sharing primary research data. Technical constraints, such as dataset size limit on repositories, often prevent the publication of large analytical datasets. To improve findability, partners have committed to using open platforms like Zenodo or institutional data repositories. The project also explores the integration of external datasets, such as those in the KU Leuven Research Data Repository (RDR).

In conclusion, the inventory highlights that a federated network is a pragmatic way to help the Belgian heritage science community move toward an open science environment. By linking scientific findings with physical heritage objects through the BALaT+ interface, DIGILAB.be will ensure that research results remain visible and accessible for future conservation and research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Heritage science in Belgium is a growing field that connects the humanities with natural sciences to study cultural heritage objects. Currently, the information generated by researchers is scattered across different institutions and universities. Much of this scientific data is not easy to find and does not follow the FAIR principles[1] (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

The DIGILAB.be project, or "DIGILAB Belgian Federated Repositories," aims to change this. The project is setting up a federated network of repositories. Instead of storing all data in one central place, each partner institution will manage its own data. The Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA) will act as a central hub using its BALaT platform to link these different sources together.

This deliverable, D.1.1.1, provides an "Inventory of existing datasets in Belgian heritage science research groups." The goal is not to list every individual file, but to provide a high-level overview of the research groups involved, how they currently handle their data, and how they plan to share it during the project. We focus specifically on research performed on physical heritage objects, as these datasets will be linked to object records in the upcoming BALaT+ interface.

2. INSTITUTIONAL DATA HABITS AND COMMITMENTS

During the initial phase of the project, visits were made to all partners to assess their current workflows. While some groups have strong publication records, few have established habits for sharing primary research data.

2.1. KIK-IRPA

KIK-IRPA is developing a repository for all object-based research data. This will be integrated into BALaT+, allowing users to search for objects, photos, and scientific data in one place. KIK-IRPA does not intend to host datasets for other institutions but will aggregate their metadata. The institute is moving towards the implementation of the open source repository software Cordra[2] to manage data as "FAIR Digital Objects"[3].

2.2. Royal Museums of Art and History (KMKG-MRAH)

The museum currently has no formal policy for publishing heritage science data. Most of this research is done in collaboration with universities or KIK-IRPA. While they use Belnet's ORFEO platform[4] for sharing publications, they do not have a dedicated data repository.

As part of this project, KMKG-MRAH will set up a Zenodo[5] community to share their heritage science data.

2.3. University of Antwerp (UAntwerpen)

Two main groups represent the university: AXIS (Physics) and ARCHES (Heritage Science). These groups produce many publications but do not usually share the underlying datasets. A major issue is the sheer size of their data, particularly from Macroscopic X-ray Fluorescence (MA-XRF) scans, which creates storage and backup challenges. The university has a dedicated community "University of Antwerp Data Repository" on Zenodo[6], but seems rarely used (yet) and not backed up by policies.

For DIGILAB.be, both AXIS and ARCHES have created specific Zenodo communities[7,8] to publish past and present research data. They will need to manage Zenodo's 50GB limit per dataset by zipping or splitting larger files.

2.4. University of Liège (ULiège)

The Centre Européen d'Archéométrie generates many papers but does not yet publish the related data. Of all partners, ULiège is the only university with an established Dataverse-based repository "ULiège Open Data Repository"[9] and an Open Science Roadmap[10] that promotes its usage. However, it is not widely used by its researchers (yet). The CEA currently keeps its datasets locally on a NAS (Network Attached Storage). They signal that most of their datasets cannot be published on the repository, because of the technical maximum dataset size limit of 2GB in Dataverse.

To improve findability, the group will create "metadata-only" records in the ULiège Dataverse. These records will describe the data and provide contact details for researchers to request access to the full datasets stored on their local NAS.

2.5. Ghent University (UGhent)

Research at UGhent is focused on Raman spectroscopy and other analysis techniques for archaeology and art. While they too generate lots of publications, there is no established practice of publishing datasets alongside their papers, and the university does not have a central data repository.

The research group has committed to setting up a dedicated Zenodo community for their research data to ensure it is available for the DIGILAB.be network.

3. OTHER SIGNIFICANT DATASETS

Outside of the project partners, KU Leuven is a major player in Belgian heritage science. The university operates the RDR (Research Data Repository)[11], which is based on the Dataverse platform. Some heritage science datasets are already public on this platform. Because the KU Leuven RDR provides metadata in standard formats (like DataCite's metadata schema), it is technically possible to include these datasets in the aggregator. This would allow researchers to find KU Leuven data alongside the data from DIGILAB.be partners, further expanding the national network.

4. CONCLUSION

The survey shows that while Belgian heritage science is technically advanced, data sharing is not yet a standard practice. Most data is stored locally and is difficult for outside researchers to find.

By setting up a federated network, DIGILAB.be allows institutions to keep control of their data while making it visible through a single portal. By adopting repository platforms like Zenodo (Invenio) and Dataverse that support open standards, such as DataCite formatted exports, combined with the BALaT+ aggregator, will help the Belgian community move toward a more open and FAIR research environment.

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